

AGEISM IN THE WORKFORCE AND IN THE INDUSTRY

Online Webinar - April 6th 14.00 UK TIME

@ITNEuroAgeism <https://euroageism.eu/>

Welcome to 'Ageism in the workforce and in the industry' webinar

- Please ensure you have signed in using your full name rather than a nickname
- Please note that all participants' microphones will be mute and cameras switched off
- We encourage you to ask questions during this session, which should be done using the 'Q & A facility' and will be answered at the end of the presentation
- Please remember that everything you type may be visible to all others who join the session, so we do advise you not to share personal data
- Please note this session will be recorded

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The screenshot displays the website's navigation menu: **About Consortium Team Research projects Research training**. Below the menu is a search bar and social media icons for Facebook and Twitter. The main content area is titled **Meet our Early Stage Researchers** and features four researcher profiles:

- Lola Casal-Sanchez**: Accompanied by a photo of her in a green jacket. Social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, Email, and Facebook are shown below her name.
- Hopf, Stefan**: Accompanied by a photo of him in a plaid shirt. Social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, Email, and Facebook are shown below his name.
- Xi, Wanyu**: Accompanied by a photo of her. Social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, Email, and Facebook are shown below her name.
- Kim, Seyoung**: Accompanied by a photo of her. Social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, Email, and Facebook are shown below her name.

Each profile includes a short bio and a list of research interests. The background of the section features a stylized map of Europe with network connections. At the bottom of the screenshot, a Windows taskbar is visible with icons for various applications like Chrome, Word, and PowerPoint.

This partial screenshot shows the **Principal Investigators** section of the website. It lists several researchers with their names and brief biographies:

- Fialová, Daniela**: Fialová Daniela, PharmD, PhD, BCCP is the Head of University...
- Georgantzi, Nena**: A trained lawyer specialized in human rights (MA, Université de Stra...
- Kydd, Angela**: Angela Kydd is Clinical Professor in Nursing at Robert Gordon Univers...
- Motel-Klingebiel, Andreas**: Andreas Motel-Klingebiel, Dr. phil., Sociologist and Gerontologist, is a Professor in Ageing and Later Life and the Head of Unit at the Division...

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Ageism and active contribution to society

- Employers-employees
- Late working life trajectories
- Welfare sustainability

Towards an age-friendly society

- Digital technologies
- Equality legislation

Ageism in access to goods and services

- Social network
- Medication management
- Dementia and care

EuroAgeism Policies briefs

<https://euroageism.eu/>

Funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Policy Report

Implications for policy and planning to foster solidarity between the generations and enhance healthy life among older adults

Work Pack

Early Stage Researcher
Hanna Brkic, Abodunrin

WP2 Leader: Prof

WP2 Deputy Lead: P

